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School Facilities Provision and Students' Disciplinary Attitudes in Public Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District

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Abstract

This study examines the extent to which the provision of school facilities predicts students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District. Two research questions were raised with their corresponding hypotheses. A correlational research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study comprised all 32969 senior secondary students in the 89 public schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District. A sample of 860 students was used for the study, derived using both a multi-stage random sampling procedure consisting of clustered, proportionate, and simple random sampling techniques. School Facilities and Disciplinary Attitude Scale (SF-DAS) was used for data collection. This instrument was validated by three lecturers. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach's alpha statistics, and a reliability coefficient of 0.88 was obtained. The data collected for the study were subjected to analysis using the simple linear regression coefficient (R) and F-value of the research questions and the hypotheses raised, respectively. The findings revealed that school libraries and laboratories significantly predict students' disciplinary attitudes. Recommendations were made, among others, that the Akwa Ibom State Government and corporate individuals should provide the school with adequate and functional library resources so as to enable the students to focus on their academics.

Keywords: school facilities, school library, school laboratory, and disciplinary attitude

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Introduction

Students' disciplinary attitude is a concept that takes into consideration the two words: discipline and attitude. Discipline, according to Egwunyenga in Lukman and Hamadi (2020), connotes training that enables an individual to develop orderly conduct and self-control, as well as self-direction. This could be regarded as an intentional adherence to norms, ethics, and etiquette guiding an effectively regulated school system. Meanwhile, attitude entails an individual's prevailing tendency to respond either favourably or unfavourably to an object, event, instruction, or institution (Ismail, 2019). It is concerned with an individual way of thinking and behaving, and this has serious implications for learners, the teachers, the immediate social group with which individual learning relates, and the school system as a whole (Yara, 2019). Therefore, discipline and attitude are two inseparable words that denote having forbearing intentions that actively engage an individual's consciousness within the formatted regulations of the school.

For instance, many studies have reported that one in every 10 students in public secondary schools in Nigeria must have been a victim of bullying (Alex-Hart, Okagua, and Opara, 2014; Salawu, 2020; Adekeye et al., 2022). Other indisciplinary attitudes commonly reported are insubordination, class disruption, disrespect for constituted authority, fighting, and cultism-related activities (Lukman et al., 2020). More worrisome is the fact that secondary schools' systems in recent times have tended to become veritable centres for gang formation, initiation into cultism, and human rights violations (raping, victimisation, among others). All these inimical variables, without exaggeration, could be responsible for poor students' academic outcomes and a rising level of education waste (in terms of students' repetition and dropout) in public secondary schools.

This insurgency in students' indisciplinary attitude in schools has been blamed on diverse variables. Many scholars, in their diverse opinions, highlighted possible factors that prone students to social vices and indisciplinary acts, to include parental socioeconomic factors, leadership variables, teachers' classroom management strategies, and students' factors (Alex-Hart et al., 2014; Adekeye et al., 2022). Although no consensus has been reached as to what actually constitutes prominent factors that promote students' indisciplinary attitudes in schools, it is the researchers' belief that the vulnerability of students to indisciplinary attitudes could stem from a lack of adequate

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and active engagement of students in the school programmes and a lack of creating functional activities that can actively engage their minds physically, socially, and psychologically.

It is essential to state that school primarily should serve as a culture room where valuable students' attitudes are built. For this character building to be in accordance with designed expectations, instruments of values must be provided to tune the students' interest, concentration, attention, attendance, and retention in line with the values of the schools. When the schools effectively fine-tune the students in this direction, it could easily engage them in profitable learning and, in turn, divert their attention from an indisciplined attitude. Some of these instruments are collectively known as school facilities.

School facilities are the most essential education factors aside the school personnel that are argued to promote effectiveness in school administration, teaching, and learning. Olugbenga (2019) considers it to be all the physical structures in the school that aid effective teaching and learning. The authors maintained that they play a vital role in the actualization of educational goals and objectives by satisfying the physical and emotional needs of the students of the school. Some of these variables that play a significant role in the educational development of learners are the school library and the school laboratory. Whether the availability of these variables can optimally curtail students' indisciplinary attitudes in secondary schools is a source of contemplation for the study.

The school library, for instance, is an important school facility and one of the most essential contributors to functional learning. Ayanlola (2019) considers the school library as a place set up to organise and preserve for use all teaching materials relevant to the school curriculum. This implies that a school library may not only serve as an asset for students' academic improvement but could also be regarded as a *sustainer* of students' academic commitment and an incubator for modelling functional, lifelong attitudes that are beneficial for self and society as a whole. However, where this valuable asset is lacking or inadequately provided in a school, the situation could deprive the students of cognitive engagement for valuable information acquisition that could generate valuable knowledge and innovation, in addition to exposing them to laziness and idleness. A series of studies have promoted the idea that the provision of school libraries is essential in promoting students' academic performance, but none has been

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able to establish its effectiveness in controlling students' excesses and indisciplinary attitudes in secondary schools.

The school laboratory is another vital school facility that, if absent, could pose a great disadvantage to effective teaching and learning process in schools. Akani (2015) defines a school laboratory as a room designed for conducting scientific exercises and experiments for the benefit of the students. This goes to say that the provision of a school laboratory has the potential to expose students to experiential learning where commitment to close observation and adherence to principles, rules, and regulations before accurate results can be obtained cannot be neglected. It is presumed that the provision of a well-equipped and functional school laboratory for students' use may assist students in developing a sense of commitment to rules and regulations guiding risky behaviours, enshrining in their consciousness zeal for discovery learning through the adoption of various valuable methods, and inculcating in their consciousness a desire to achieve results. It is premised on this position that the researchers believe that the provision of functional laboratories may not only benefit students by improving their academic performance but could ultimately assist them in building formidable disciplinary dispositions. Whether this presumption is true is a source of contemplation for this study.

Empirically, Ayaz, Ali, Khan, Ullah, and Ullah (2016) assessed the impact of school libraries on students' academic achievement at the secondary school level in the southern districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The study was descriptive in nature. The population of the study consisted of all students and teachers of government secondary schools in the southern districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The sample of the study consisted of 700 respondents, of whom 500 were male and female students and 200 were teachers of twelve (12) secondary schools in the districts of Bannu and Lakki Marwat. A questionnaire was utilised for data collection. Percentage, frequency, and linear regression were used for data analysis. The results showed that the majority of respondents views indicated that school libraries have a great impact on students, academic achievements at the secondary school level in the southern districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The present study would benefit from this study in the area of design, though the dependent variable considered is different from the current study.

Sakiyo (2022) assessed students' attitudes towards practical laboratory work in physics in senior secondary schools in Yola North, Yola South, and Girei Local

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Government Areas of Adamawa State. Twelve senior secondary schools were randomly sampled, and 72 students participated in the study. A modified Interest Inventory questionnaire with a Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of 0.86 was used. Two research questions and one hypothesis guided the study. The mean and standard deviation were used to determine students' attitudes toward practical laboratory work in physics, while a t-test was used to establish if there was any significant difference between male and female students' attitudes toward practical laboratory work in physics. The study indicated that the students have a negative attitude toward practical laboratory work in physics. The study also shows that there was no significant difference in male and female students' attitudes toward practical laboratory work in physics ($t = 307$, $t_{crit} = 1.658$). It was recommended, among others, that teacher training institutions should reappraise the adequacy of their teacher training programmes so as to equip teachers with competency skills to teach adequately according to the requirements of the physics curriculum. The purpose of this study was to gain knowledge about the assessment pattern of the present work. However, the present work differs in dimension from it as it considers the impact of laboratory provision on disciplinary attitude instead of academic attitude. From the foregoing, it is researchers' belief that school facilities may have an intense influence on students' disciplinary attitudes, which may fuel or hinder their desire to exceed expectations and achieve quality academic attainment. Therefore, whether these school facilities—the school library, school laboratory, school sports facilities, and classroom blocks—predict students' disciplinary attitudes in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district and the extent of the predictions was the main focus of this study.

Statement of the Problem

Every school system ought to have been a centre where every period revolving around the students is participating, interesting, and engaging within a specified and established discipline. Unfortunately, a walk to some public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, most especially the northeast senatorial district, shows students loitering within the school compound and even outside the school premises aimlessly. Also worrisome is the fact that in most cases, students are found in classrooms gossiping, throwing tantrums, making noise, stealing, fighting, bullying, and vandalising classmates' property as well as that of the school. In other cases, some students, instead of concentrating on self-

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learning during lesson-free hours, are often involved in planning for revenge during break periods. These and many more challenges of indiscipline often culminated in large-scale violence, cult-related engagement, interschool rioting, and the destruction of school properties.

However, many studies attributed these students' social menace to poor or ineffective school leadership factors, teachers' classroom management strategies, teachers' lackadaisical attitude to teaching, ineffective interpersonal relationships with students, and poor students' variables (poor self-concept, self-esteem, self-confidence, self-acceptance, and self-appreciation) emanating from ineffective home front (poor parent social support, and low socioeconomic implications). To this effect, diverse recommendations have been suggested and adopted by the school managers, but the issue of students' indisciplinary attitudes is still on the rise. It could be that these facilities (library and school laboratory) are not readily available for students, resulting in their unruly behavior. It is on the basis of this that this study becomes imperative.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine the extent to which school facilities provision predicts students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district. Other specific purposes of the study were to:

1. Examine the extent to which the provision of a school library predicts students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district.
2. Examine the extent to which the provision of a school laboratory predicts students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district.

Significance of the Study

The underlying importance of school facilities may not necessarily end in improving students' academic performance but could promote their disciplinary attitude as well. Therefore, the findings of this study would benefit the state government, the principals, students, and the school community.

To the government, the findings would provide them with valuable details about the potency of school facilities in managing students' behavioural anomalies. This

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would encourage the government to adequately fund the schools and ensure routine supervision of the funds to ensure plans for the provision of these essential school facilities are properly implemented without sharp practices.

The findings would equally benefit the principals by promoting their awareness of the importance of the provision of standard school facilities in inculcating a valuable disciplinary attitude in students. To the school community, the findings would expose to them the significance of assisting in the provision of basic school facilities to schools in the management of students' indisciplinary attitudes. Their provision of these facilities and protection of the available ones would translate to moulding formidable and well-disciplined students with lifelong values of loyalty to constituted authority, rule adherence, innovativeness, functional competitiveness, and zealously. The long-run behavioural effect of these values would transcend having better citizens and a peaceful community. Finally, the findings would add valuable literature in the area of school facility provision and students' indisciplinary attitudes, as well as provide resources for further future research.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the extent to which the provision of school libraries predicts students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district?
2. To what extent does the provision of school laboratories predict students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district?

Research Hypotheses

The null hypotheses formulated for the study were tested at .05 level of significance, thus:

1. The extent to which the provision of school libraries predicts students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district is not significant.
2. The extent to which the provision of school laboratories predicts students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district is not significant.

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Research Method

A correlational research design was adopted to examine the variability of the variables as raised in the research purposes. This design emphasises testing for the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variable. The population of the study comprised all 32969 senior secondary two students in the 89 public schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District. (Statistics Division of the State Secondary Education Board, Uyo, 2023). A sample of 860 senior secondary two (SS2) students was used for the study. The sample was derived using a multi-stage random sampling procedure consisting of clustered, proportionate, and simple random sampling techniques. This multi-stage approach was used to segment the study area into smaller units with the expectation of giving equal chances of representation and participation in the study.

A questionnaire entitled School Facilities and Disciplinary Attitude Scale (SF-DAS) was used for the study. The research instrument, SF-DAS, was used to elicit information from the respondents on the availability, adequacy, and effectiveness of independent sub-variables (school library, school laboratory) and the disciplinary attitude of the students. SF-DAS was sectioned into two: A and B. Section A elicited personal information from the respondents, such as names of the school and gender. Section B was clustered into two sub-sections, each representing an independent sub-variable. Meanwhile, each of these clusters had five items structured on four modified rating scales of very high extent (VHE), high extent (HE), low extent (LE), and very low extent (VLE) statements. These statements were presented from a positive perspective; hence, the coding was VHE, representing 4, HE, 3, LE, 2, and VLE, is 1. The instrument (SF-DAS) was face-validated by three lecturers (one from Measurement and Evaluation, Guidance and Counselling, and the others from Curriculum Studies/Management and Planning) in the Faculty of Education, University of Uyo. The face validation of the instrument was done with strict adherence to the research questions raised so as to ensure that the test items reflected all the details in the blue print. The lecturers scrutinised the SF-DAS items for suitability and clarity; added any other items that were relevant but not included in the instrument; and removed irrelevant or ambiguous statements in order to improve the strength and structure of the items. Their comments and corrections on the items' clarity, appropriateness of language, ability to elicit accurate information, and suitability in line with the specific objectives were integrated into the final version of the instrument.

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The reliability coefficient of SF-DAS was determined using the scores of the 30 respondents (students) from non-participating schools obtained after the trial testing. These respondents were part of the study's population that was not selected for the main study. The data collected from the trial testing was used to ascertain the internal consistency of the instrument using an inter-item approach. The reliability of the instrument was estimated from the data collected using the Cronbach alpha statistical tool (r). The reliability coefficient of 0.88 was obtained and was used to assess the strength of the instrument's consistency in eliciting information for the study at any given time. A letter of researcher's introduction was given by the researcher's head of department (HOD) to the principals of the participating schools, informing them of the researcher's research engagement and requesting the release of essential but required information mainly for the purpose of the research and development.

After the permission had been granted by the principals, the researcher gathered data from students in the sampled schools through the administration of SF-DAS. This was done after the researcher briefed them on the essentialities of the study in the enhancement of public secondary schools' disciplinary status. At the end of the data collection stage, the instrument's valid return rate was 100 percent, thus approving the validity of the data collected in answering research questions and testing the corresponding hypotheses formulated. The simple linear regression coefficient (R) was used to answer research questions, and the F-value of the simple linear regression statistic was used to test the null hypotheses formulated for the study.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the extent to which the provision of school libraries predicts students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district?

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Table 1: Simple Linear Regression Analysis of provision of school libraries on students' disciplinary attitudes

Variables	R	R ²	Extent of Prediction	Adjusted R ²	Remarks
Provision of school library	0.943	0.890	89.0%	0.890	Very High Extent of Prediction
Students' disciplinary attitude					

Source: Researcher's survey (2023)

In table 1, the results reveal that R-value is 0.943 and R² is 0.890. The R-value of 0.943 indicates positive and very high extent of prediction, while R² value of 0.890 which is the coefficient of determination, shows the extent to which provision of school libraries predicts students' disciplinary attitudes. In addition, 89.0% variance in students' disciplinary attitudes is predicted by the provision of school libraries. This means that the provision of school libraries highly predicts students' disciplinary attitudes.

Research Question 2

To what extent does the provision of school laboratories predict students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district?

Table 2: Simple Linear Regression Analysis of the Provision of School Laboratories on Students' Disciplinary Attitudes

Variables	R	R ²	Extent of Prediction	Adjusted R ²	Remarks
Provision of school laboratory	0.512	0.262	26.2%	0.261	Moderate Extent of Prediction
Students' disciplinary attitude					

Source: Researcher's survey (2023)

In table 2, the results reveal that R-value is 0.512 and R² is 0.262. The R-value of 0.512 indicates positive and moderate extent of prediction, while R² value of 0.262 which is the coefficient of determination shows the extent to which the provision of school laboratories predicts students' disciplinary attitudes. In addition, 26.2% variance

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in students' disciplinary attitudes is predicted by the provision of school laboratories. This means that the provision of a school laboratory moderately predicts students' disciplinary attitudes.

Hypothesis 1: The extent to which the provision of school libraries predicts students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district is not significant.

Table 3: Simple Linear Regression Analysis of Prediction of the Provision of School Library on Student' Disciplinary Attitudes

Variables	Sources of Variation	Sum of Square	Df	MS	F-cal	F-crit	Decision at p<.05
Provision of school library Student' disciplinary attitude	Regression	796.114286	1	796.114286	6949.80*	3.86	Reject H ₀
	Residual	98.285714	858	.115			

*= Significant at .05 alpha level. Source: Researcher's survey (2023)

The results of table 3 show that the calculated F- value of 6949.80 is greater than the critical F- value of 3.86 at .05 level of significance, with 1 and 858 degree of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis that "the extent to which the provision of school libraries predicts students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district is not significant" was rejected. This means that the provision of school libraries significantly predicts students' disciplinary attitudes.

Hypothesis 2: The extent to which the provision of school laboratories predicts students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district is not significant.

Table 4: Simple Linear Regression Analysis of Prediction of Provision of School Laboratory on Student' Disciplinary Attitude

Variables	Sources of Variation	Sum of Square	Df	MS	F-cal	F-crit	Decision at p<.05
Provision of school laboratory Student' disciplinary attitude	Regression	234.243142	1	234.243142	304.44*	3.86	Reject H ₀
	Residual	660.156858	858	.769			

*= Significant at .05 alpha level. Source: Researcher's survey (2023)

The results of table 4 show that the calculated F- value of 304.44 is greater than the critical F- value of 3.86 at .05 level of significance, with 1 and 858 degree of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis that "the extent to which the provision of school laboratory predicts students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district is not significant" was rejected. This means that the provision of school laboratories significantly predict students' disciplinary attitudes.

Discussion of the Findings

The findings based on Hypothesis one, which stated that the extent to which the provision of school libraries predicts students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district is not significant, revealed that there is a very high extent of prediction between the provision of school libraries and students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district. The provision of a school library accounts for 89.0% of the variation in students' disciplinary attitudes.

The result also shows that provision of libraries significantly predicts students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district. This finding indicates that students' disciplinary attitudes will increase to a very high extent as schools' managements effectively make libraries to be available in schools. The provision of a school library is an important factor that can influence students' disciplinary attitudes in secondary schools. The provision of a well-equipped and a well-stocked school library can encourage students to read, learn, and explore new ideas. Students who have access to a variety of books and other resources are more likely to develop a positive attitude towards learning, which can translate into a better disciplinary attitude overall.

The findings of this study agree with the findings of Ayaz, Ali, Khan, Ullah, and Ullah (2016) which revealed, among others, that there is a positive relationship between school libraries and students' academic achievement at secondary school level in southern districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

The findings based on Hypothesis two, which stated that the extent to which the provision of school laboratories predicts students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district is not significant, revealed that there is a moderate extent of prediction between the provision of school laboratories and students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district. The provision of school laboratories accounts for 26.2% of the variation in students' disciplinary attitudes.

The result also shows that the provision of school laboratories significantly predicts students' disciplinary attitudes in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom Northeast senatorial district. This finding indicates that students' disciplinary attitudes will increase to a moderate extent as schools' managements effectively make laboratories to be available in schools. The provision of a school laboratory is an important factor that can influence students' disciplinary attitudes in secondary schools. Providing school laboratories with the necessary equipment and resources can help students develop practical skills and engage in hands-on learning experiences. Students who have access to well-equipped laboratories are more likely to enjoy science and other practical subjects, which can positively impact their disciplinary attitudes.

The findings of this study agree with the findings of Sakiyo (2022) which revealed, among others, that physics laboratory has the most significant effect on the students' attitudes.

Conclusion / Recommendations

The study concluded that the provision of school facilities (a well-equipped library and laboratory) has the potential to greatly manage insecurity and indiscipline among the students in schools.

In light of the conclusion drawn from the findings of the study, the following were recommended:

- i. Akwa Ibom State Government, and corporate individuals should provide schools with adequate and functional library resources so as to enable the students to focus on their academics.

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- ii. Akwa Ibom State Government, and corporate individuals should provide schools with adequate and functional laboratories as well as create platforms to adequately engage students in learning competitions.

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